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THE PLACE OF THE OLDER ADULTS IN COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN AGBONMWONABA VILLAGE IN OVIA NORTH EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EDO STATE

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Abstract

Aging population has accelerated significantly in the 21st century, posing a considerable developmental challenge, particularly for nations that are not prepared to address its consequences. To mitigate these challenges, it is crucial to encourage active participation of older individuals in matters affecting their lives. However, reports indicate that older persons have not been fully engaged in the development process, especially in community development activities. This study assessed the extent of older adults' participation in community development activities in Agbonmwonba village, Ovia North East Local Government Area of Edo State Nigeria. It sought to identify factors hindering their participation in the community development in the study area. The study employed a descriptive survey design incorporating quantitative method, a sample of 399 older persons were randomly selected from a target population of 176,338 in Agbonmwonba village. The study found that the low participation of older persons in community development activities exposed them to poverty, limited access to resources, inadequate representation in decision-making processes, poor public services, social isolation, and deteriorating physical and mental health. Consequently, this marginalization left them vulnerable and excluded from community development activities, further exacerbating their social isolation and marginalization. The study recommends that the government and other stakeholders should take proactive measures to encourage and support older persons, ensuring they have equal opportunities to participate in community development activities and contribute to finding solutions to their challenges. The findings of this study can inform the development of policies, strategies, and programs at both local and national levels..

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BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Growing and aging is a natural process that every individual experiences. As we grow, we encounter various negative and positive experiences that change our perception of life. Elderly people have always been the treasure of our families. However, in the modern society of the 21st century, not only has the number of elderly people increased but

also the cases of the elderly being abused, harassed, and abandoned in Nigeria. More children are now leaving their parents alone or are sending them to old-age homes.

In societies across the globe, the elderly population holds a unique and indispensable position within their communities. Their accumulated wisdom, experiences, and continued engagement play a vital role in shaping the social, economic, and cultural landscape. The elderly, often referred to as seniors or elders, represent a demographic group characterized by advanced age, typically defined as individuals aged 65 and older. While aging is commonly associated with retirement and a decrease in productivity, research indicates that the elderly remain active contributors to community development in various capacities (Hinterlong, 2018). Their roles encompass a wide range of activities, including but not limited to volunteerism, caregiving, leadership, and cultural preservation (Kim & Kim, 2020). One of the primary roles of the elderly in community development is their function as repositories of knowledge and experience. Across cultures, elders are esteemed for their accumulated wisdom, which encompasses not only practical skills and expertise but also cultural traditions, oral histories, and moral values (Bengtson & Settersten, 2016). Moreover, the elderly contribute significantly to the social fabric of their communities through their involvement in caregiving and support networks. As parents, grandparents, and caregivers, they play essential roles in nurturing and sustaining family units, providing emotional support, childcare, and intergenerational bonding (Lowenstein et al., 2019). Additionally, many seniors are actively engaged in volunteer activities, community organizations, and religious institutions, where they contribute their time, skills, and resources to address social needs and promote community well-being (Dury et al., 2015). Despite their invaluable contributions, the elderly in the society are at higher risk of marginalization and inequality. The same sentiments are echoed by Garavan, Winder & McGee, (2016) who note that level of marginalization of elderly people in social, political, economic, as well as cultural activities are growing to an alarming level.

Furthermore, the low participation of the elderly significantly impacts their overall well-being. Hence, it is imperative to shed light on the challenges faced by elderly, particularly those residing in the Agbonmaoba community within the Ovia North East Local Government Area of Edo State. This entails documenting their capabilities as well as the barriers hindering their involvement in community development initiatives. The insights gleaned from this data can serve as a valuable resource for policymaking and addressing the concerns of older persons. It requires a concerted effort involving political support, allocation of resources, and collaboration among communities, development partners, and governmental bodies. Such evidence-based approaches are essential for meeting the increasing needs of older persons while simultaneously fostering economic empowerment and fostering sustainable community growth.

Statement of Research Problem

Population of older persons worldwide has increased significantly. This change comes at a point when nations are not able or adequately prepared to address arising needs involving older persons. This increase in population of older persons in Agbonmaoba community, Ovia north east local government area of Edo state presents a unique challenge that needs to be addressed through age appropriate policy interventions. Additionally, assumptions are made that older persons are reliant on their communities for social, psychological and material support. Other studies reveal that traditional structures for care of older persons have broken leaving them vulnerable and disenfranchised. There is need to

thus emphasize the capacity of older persons that can be utilized for their benefit and that of the wider community as active participants in the development of their communities

Older persons are however not entirely dependent on the wider community for support but rather contribute to building of their communities in the social, economic, political and cultural spheres. Studies conducted suggest that there is limited participation of older persons in community development and this presents a unique opportunity to research more and identify why their contribution is still limited. There is also limited research on how this group contributes to building of their local economies at the social, economic and political levels. This study therefore sought to address this gap. It is against this backdrop that this study sought to assess older person's place in community development activities, document factors influencing their participation/place, establishing how low participation affects their well-being as well as suggest measures to enhance their integration on issues affecting them.

Objective of the Study

The aim of the study was to assess the place of the elderly in community development in Agbonmaoba community, Ovia North Local Government Area, of Edo State. While the specific objectives are: to

1. assess the level of participation of older adults in community development activities in Agbonmwonba community.
2. identify the factors influencing the participation of older adults in community development activities specifically within the Agbonmaoba community.

LITERATURE REVIEW

[Schutte, \(2016\)](#) defines community development as a process whereby ongoing affirmative change among people living in the same area is realized by participating in the process to identify needs and actions with minimal outside interference. Community development enables people to participate in activities for the sole purpose of making their lives better. Participation allows people to reason, agree, plan and act in determining their lives. It permits members of the community to come together to plan, offer solutions and take action towards developing the social, economic, environmental and cultural aspects of their community [Udoh, \(2015\)](#). Emphasis is placed in the importance of participation as a means of solidification of local communities.

The emphasis of people participation in development activities is a key factor in empowering community. Most institutions and organizations have adopted this mode of operation to enhance active participation of all people in all facets of strategic plan development and execution. The notion of grass roots participation in community development programs has advanced in human empowerment and development process. The government agencies and other stakeholders in community development continue to either actively or passively exclude elderly in community development arena. This limits their involvement in decision making on matters relating to their life thereby denying them access and utilization of resources and their contribution toward community development [Range, \(2005\)](#) that people's full participation in development programs support to bring fast and real socio-economic change that fosters development. Active ageing allows older persons to live meaningful and rewarding lives, contribute positively to their communities and minimize on health expenses associated with non-activity ([WHO, 2018](#)).

Scholars argue that discussions on issues and concepts of ageing and old age in a sub-Saharan context should exercise caution and sensitivity.

According to [Prunty \(2014\)](#), the conception of chronological age has far less importance in “developing” countries. [Garavan, Winder & McGee, \(2017\)](#) observes that even though the process of getting old is a biological reality, it can be termed as also socially constructed and determined differently by different cultures. However, it should be noted sometimes registration of births has been poor in Nigeria, especially in Agbonmaoba community in Ovia north local government area of Edo state, and many older persons do not know their age in exact terms of years. Therefore, it is of great importance to critically reflect on the problem of the definition of old age and how this consequently affects older persons' access to services, policy, and resource allocations ([HelpAge International, 2017](#); [Scharf et al, 2017](#)).

Research studies have raised two key concerns concerning how to examine participation among older persons in development activities. First through establishing the extent of involvement among older persons and secondly to ascertain what influences participation or lack of participation in old age. [Scharf and Keating, \(2015\)](#) believe that having this knowledge will guide in the development of appropriate policies and interventions that address the issue of low participation among older persons. Additionally, such policies may encourage social inclusion among older persons. This will help to develop potential policy and practice responses to older person's low participation and may encourage social inclusion among older adults and promote social cohesion among community dwellers.

Place of Older Persons in Community Development Activities

The study looks at the four aspects of development that encompasses individual interactions with family and larger community through social participation, their contribution to the economic domain of development, the civic and political participation and cultural participation. These domains are discussed in detail in subsequent subheadings in regards to older person's involvement in community development activities.

Older Persons Participation in Social Activities

According to [Dehi and Mohammadi, \(2020\)](#), social participation of older persons includes their involvement through social interactions, participation in community activities, sharing of resources, networking and maintaining social contacts. It allows interactions among community members. It affords individuals an opportunity to engage in socialization, recreation, taking part in social-cultural activities and building on social capital. It looks at interactions of individuals' participation in community activities, civic activities and even cultural activities. Social relationships are viewed as a positive way of ensuring healthy active ageing and participation [Croezen, \(2016\)](#).

According to [Monasch, \(2018\)](#), different groups perceive relationships differently. The degree of sustaining these relationships include meeting up, talking on the phone among others. These vary from one group to another. Social relationships can be classified into structural and functional distinctiveness. The structural aspect looks at the rate of interactions and sources of networks. These interactions look at regularity of contacts and interactions with family, friends and neighbours. Evidence suggests that satisfaction with close contacts was associated with better health [Croezen, \(2016\)](#). It also looks at other links

or interactions with other family members whom they live with. Social interactions with other family members living away are also considered (Kneale, 2015).

Social support is importance for older persons. This is a crucial prerequisite in old age to cushion older persons against many age-related effects. Ageing is linked to increased risk of exposure to various problems such as start of chronic conditions, declining sources of income, poor health, and loss of spouse and confidants Nemeroff, et al, (2016). Societal support is also often associated with improved health among the older persons. According to Dai, et al, (2016) social support is highly connected with good health. Social support was also linked to improved mental health for older persons in a study that sought to assess social capital in relation to mental well-being (Nygvist et al, 2014)

Older persons are mostly exposed to loss of social relationships either through loss of close contacts, spouses and migration of family members. Health complications associated with old age as well as mobility challenges limits older people's ability to frequently interact with the wider community. The study further established that social and emotional solitude and seclusion was a significant problem for rural older persons. The study notes that these issues could be consequences of low participation in social interactions and other related opportunities. Studies have also established that quantity and quality of social network contacts affect health of older persons. These networks are measured by looking at the frequency of contacts with close ties such as family and friends, and the satisfaction derived from these interactions. Evidence suggests that satisfaction derived from having close social contact was related to better physical and mental health among older persons. This study seeks to establish whether this is the case with older persons in the Agbonmaoba community considering that due to demographic changes, the family unit has changed and older persons are increasing finding themselves living alone and having to support themselves.

Theoretical Framework: Political Economy of Ageing Theory

This theory is a macro level third generation theory. This theory is centered on the assumption that social class determines a person's access to resources as well as the fact that leading groups within the general public try to sustain their own interests by spreading class disparities. In their analysis, political economists note that older persons face various challenges emanating from government stratification, economic situation, unequal allocation as well as distribution of resources. The theory main focus is on structural challenges that bring about inequality and less on individual reasons such as the reduced physical or mental capacity of older persons Estes (2020), Townsend (1986); Walker (2019). This study borrows from the theory by looking at the legitimacy of social interventions focusing on older persons; government authority and control, capital, and labour associations on aging as well as the impact of social policy for older persons Estes (2020). The study uses the theory to explain how structural factors and social policy environment and processes influence place of older persons in political, social, and economical aspects of development and their integration in ageing of the individual and at the societal level Estes (2020).

In the context of this study, social forces of politics and the socio- economic power have influence on resource allocation which acts as a determinant to ageing condition through unequal allocation of resources. This form of inequality tends to diminish the power of the older persons in the societal initiatives owed to the loss of their power and influence in the society Estes (2020). Characteristics such as class, occupation, social status and sexual

characteristics seem to determine the pattern of the older persons' experience in life together with their economic and political power; this acts as the basic foundation of curving in the opportunities associated with later life (Bytheway, 2019).

This theory puts emphasis on welfare of the older persons and its significant contribution to the socio-economic structure of the society which is attributed to their low productivity thus loss of worth in the society and its developmental initiatives Estes (2020). It seeks to find out how the older persons are treated in the society, their definition and the cause of isolation and inequality in regard to resources in the society Estes et al. (2020). Political economy theory brings out the development of individual issues to public issues which is actually a societal concern in terms of gender, class and age among others.

In this research, the study adopts this theory to demonstrate that social, economic and political structures and ideologies shape the social policies that are meant to cushion older persons against the challenges arising from their inability to participate in development activities. As demonstrated in the literature, older persons are not able to fully explore their potential due to the existing social structures that limit their participation capacities and capabilities, instead their functionality is determined by public policy and social and economic structures which are determined by the social political economy (Townsend, 2017).

Political economists argue that structural forces created by the political economy shapes the social welfare of the older persons and their personal experience which is manifested in broader societal level. Just as Estes noted, older person's participation in political and civic activities is highly influenced by interactions at community level, social norms and practices, self-interest driven by what one perceives to get from their involvement. Low participation of older persons in these spheres contributes to their loss of power over their situations, autonomy and their influence of issues that affect them. This creates a need to examine the broader issues of civil/political, economic, culture and social issues that affects the productivity opportunities of people in the society, in this case the older persons.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is survey research which involved the quantitative method. Survey research design which inherently makes for the identification of a sample of the research population involved the application of quantitative technique. The quantitative technique was utilized with the administration of questionnaires, the design was considered appropriate because it involved the sampling of opinions of respondents. The population under study consisted of older persons drawn from Agbonmaoba community in Ovia north east. According to Ovia North East statistics department, 2021, the population consists of 176338 of older persons by the year 2021. The primary respondents included 400 older people. . This study thus selected a sample with 95% precision as suggested by (Yamane, 1967). The 95% precision was chosen to achieve the desired sample size which was manageable owing to the time and resources available in conducting this study.

$$n = \frac{N}{(1+N(e)^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{176338}{(1+176338(0.05)^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{176338}{(1+176338)(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{176338}{(1+440.845)}$$

$$n = \frac{176338}{441.845}$$

$$n = 399.0$$

$$n = 400$$

Where; n = Sample size, N = Population size, e = Desired marginal error, 1= Constant

From the analysis above, the sample size was 400

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1- Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Measurements	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	199	49.7%
	Female	200	50.1%
	Total	399	100.0
Age	54-59years	42	10.5%
	60-64years	74	18.5%
	65-69 years	210	52.6%
	70-74years	34	8.5%
	75 years – Above	39	9.8%
Total	399	100.0	
Religion	Christianity	241	60.4%
	Islam	46	11.5%
	Traditional	112	28.1%
	Others	0	0%
	Total	399	100.0
Marital status	Single	180	45.1%
	Married	190	47.6%
	Separated	10	2.5%
	Divorced	10	2.5%
	Widow/Widower	9	2.2%
	Total	399	100.0
Occupation	Government employee	90	22.6%
	Non-government employee	180	45.1%
	Retiree	90	22.6%
	Self-employed	30	7.5%
	Unemployed	9	2.2%
	Total	399	100.0

Source: Field work, 2024

Table.1. Showed gender distribution of the respondents, out of the 399 Respondents that were sampled for the study, the result revealed that 49.7% were males while 50.1% were females. The females are more than men this implies that women constitute a larger population of the older population when compared to men in Agbonmoba community. The table 1 above showed the age distribution of respondents, the result from the table revealed that 42 of them, representing 10.5% 4-59 years; while 74, representing 18.5% are within the age range of 60-64 years. Also 210 of the respondents, representing 52.6% of the entire respondents' falls within ages 65-69 years. However, 34 of them, representing 8.5% are within the age range of 70-74 years; and also 39 of them, representing 9.8% of the

respondents fall within ages 75years and above. Therefore, majority of the respondents who participated in this study fall within ages 65-69 years.

The table above shows religious distribution of respondents, the result from the table revealed that of the 399 respondents, 241 of the respondents representing 60.4% were Christians, 112 of the respondents representing 28.1% were from the Islamic religion; while 46 of the respondents representing 11.5% were from the African Tradition religion, Other religious group recorded zero respondent in the study. Therefore, it can be said that the majority of respondents in this study were Christians. The table above shows marital distribution of respondents, the data on the marital distribution of respondents revealed that 45.1% are single, the study further shows that 47.6% are married, also 2.5% and 2.5% are separated and divorced respectively, while 2.2% are Widow/Widower, therefore majority of the respondents who participated in the study were married.

The table above shows occupational distribution of respondents, the result on the occupation of respondents revealed that 22.6% of the respondents were Government employees, also 45.1% of the respondents were non-government employees, while 22.6% of the respondents were Retirees, while 7.5%and 2.2% of the respondents were both self-employed and unemployed respectively. This shows that majority of the respondents who participated in the study were non-government employees.

Analysis Relating to Specific Objectives

This was designed to address specific objectives to provide an analysis on the place of the elderly in community development in Agbonmoba Local Government Area, of Edo State. Their responses and analysis are presented below.

Table 2: Distribution on to what extent do older persons participate in community development activities?

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Who do you live with currently?	Children	260	65.2%
	Relative	134	33.5%
	Alone	5	1.3%
	Total	399	100.0
Do older person help with community project	YES	295	73.9%
	NO	100	25.0%
	Don't know	4	1.0%
	Total	399	100.0
Do older people take part in making our community better	Yes	263	65.9%
	No	131	32.8%
	Don't know	5	1.3%
	Total	399	100.0
Are older individuals involved in improving our neighborhood	YES	100	25.0%
	NO	295	73.9%
	Don't know	4	1.0%
	Total	399	100.0

Source: Field work, 2024

The data on the distribution on to what extent do older persons participate in community development activities, table 2 indicates that older people play an active and significant role in community development initiatives. Despite the challenges associated with aging, a considerable number of older individuals are actively engaged in various community projects, making invaluable contributions to society. The data reveals that older

people can and do participate in community development endeavors. It shows that 65.2% of older individuals are staying with their children, while 35.5% are residing with relatives, and 1.3% reported living alone. Furthermore, when asked about their involvement in community projects, 73.9% responded affirmatively, indicating their active participation. Similarly, when questioned about their role in making the community better, 65.9% responded positively, showing their commitment to community improvement. However, when specifically asked about involvement in neighborhood improvement, only 25.0% responded positively.

These statistics highlight the active involvement of older people in community development, indicating that they not only contribute to addressing community needs but also foster a sense of belonging and purpose among older adults. These findings underscore the importance of acknowledging and supporting the valuable role that older people play in community development efforts. As our population ages, it becomes increasingly essential to recognize the contributions of older individuals to society, their experience, skills, and wisdom are invaluable assets in community development. Moreover, their active involvement helps bridge generational gaps and ensures that community project are inclusive and representative of all age groups. Efforts to engage older people in community development should be encouraged and supported. This may include providing opportunities for older individuals to participate in decision-making processes, offering training and skill development programs tailored to their needs, and creating age-friendly environments that enable their active participation. Therefore, older people are not only capable but also eager to contribute to community development. By recognizing and supporting their valuable role, we can create more inclusive and vibrant communities for people of all ages.

Table 3: Distribution on what are the factors contributing to older person's participation in community development activities in Agbomaoba community

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Do certain factors make elderly people want to help out in making our community	Yes	290	72.7%
	No	100	25.0%
	Don't know	9	2.3%
	Total	399	100
Do elderly people join in community improvement efforts	Yes	150	37.6%
	No	240	60.1%
	Don't know	9	2.3%
	Total	399	100
Does anything encourage elderly people to get involved in improving their community	Yes	290	72.7%
	No	100	25.0%
	Don't know	9	2.3%
	Total	399	100
Is there any reason for the elderly people to join in community project	Yes	150	37.6%
	No	240	60.1%
	Don't know	9	2.3%
	Total	399	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The data on the factors contributing to older persons' participation in community development activities in Agbonmaoba community, as shown in Table.3, revealed some insightful findings. According to the data, 72.7% of respondents affirmed that certain factors motivate elderly people to engage in community development activities, while 25.0% said no, and 2.3% indicated that they didn't know. Furthermore, when asked if elderly people actively join in community improvement efforts, 37.6% responded affirmatively, while

60.1% answered negatively, and 2.3% were unsure. Investigating this issue further, 72.7% of respondents indicated that there are factors encouraging elderly people to get involved in improving their community, while 25.0% said no, and 2.3% were unsure. However, when asked if there are reasons why elderly people might choose not to participate in community projects, 60.1% of respondents said yes, 37.6% said no, and 2.3% were unsure. These findings shed light on the complex dynamics that influence older persons' participation in community development activities. While a significant percentage of elderly individuals are motivated to contribute to community development, there are also barriers that deter their active involvement.

Understanding these factors is crucial for designing effective strategies to enhance elderly participation in community development initiatives. The data suggests that a majority of elderly individuals are indeed interested in contributing to community development. However, various factors may influence their level of involvement. Efforts to encourage elderly participation should focus on addressing the barriers identified in this study while leveraging the factors that motivate older persons to engage in community development activities. By creating an environment that supports and encourages the active participation of elderly individuals, communities can benefit from their valuable experience, knowledge, and skills. Therefore, understanding the factors that influence older persons' participation in community development activities is crucial for promoting their active involvement. By addressing barriers and leveraging motivating factors, communities can create more inclusive and vibrant environments for people of all ages.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first objective evaluated the extent to which the older persons participate in community development activities. Results established that older adults participated in all domains of community development. However, their level of participation was still very low. The second objective sought to establish factors influencing participation of older persons in community development. Determinants of participation in community activities were dynamic. Interviews with key informants also revealed that failure of public strategies, policies and institutions to support, enhance and uphold equitable access to productive resources, properties/assets and chances limited participation of older persons in community development activities. Interestingly, those older persons who had built their social and economic capital over the years either through employment or business reported that they actively participated in community activities and were often given positions to head various community forums/projects. However, this was a minority of them since a big percentage as reported in chapter four faced social and economic challenges that limited their ability to participate in development activities.

The third objective evaluated the effect of low participation on older person's well-being. Inability for them to get involved in development activities resulted to effects like stress and depression taking them further away from the rest of the community, poor physical health coupled by inadequate resources to access basic needs including health services. Inadequate income meant they could not meet their basic needs while poor infrastructure and lack of civic education denied them a chance to participate in public forums and have their voices heard which resulted to having their needs not being addressed by projects designed by the government and other development partners. The net effect of their limited potential to fully participate in development activities exposed

them to social exclusion which made them more vulnerable and limited their capacity to engage in community development and enhance their wellbeing

CONCLUSION

The study established that although older persons are generally engaged in community development, their level of participation, influence and control on issues that affect them is relatively very low compared to other population groups. While advanced age generally implies limited capacity to be equally productive, other factors such as gender, economic situation, lack of proper policies also affected them and hindered their ability to actively participate in community development. This exposed them to various challenges such as poor health, low income, and depression among others leaving them vulnerable.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

1. There is need for the government to create a conducive environment that will enhance and diversify their sources of income by improving and enhancing already existing policies aimed at creating economic will power of older persons.
2. There is need for collaborations by stakeholders to intensify civic education to older people especially on the importance of public participation on issues that directly or indirectly affect them.
3. Older adults should strive to engage in community activities and in particular participate in public participation forums where views are gathered and used to influence policy interventions, budget allocation and service delivery. This way they are able to influence decisions on issues affection them

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